

Table 1: Data Extraction Form

Item	Values	RQ
Source	IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library or DBLP	-
Publication title	-	-
Author(s)	-	-
Publication date	-	-
Keywords	-	-
Citations	-	-
Type of research questions (Type of study)	Classification of research questions in Software Engineering articles: method or means of development; method for analysis or evaluation; design, evaluation, or analysis of a particular instance; generalization or characterization; feasibility study or exploration	
Research questions	-	-
Study proposal	technique, methodology, method, framework, tool, process, guideline or principle	RQ1 and RQ3
Context of the study	industry, academy or author's illustration	-
Software Engineering Stage	SWEBOK defines the main stages within the context of Software Engineering as: planning, software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	RQ2
Recommendations or key findings of the study	-	RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3
Study limitations	-	-